

Assessing the National Health Insurance (NHI) in South Africa: Policy Formulation, Stakeholder engagement and Implementation Challenges

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Abstract

This study aims to assess the National Health Insurance (NHI) in South Africa by examining its policy formulation, stakeholder engagement and implementation challenges. The research utilises a document analysis approach, reviewing key policy documents such as the NHI Bill, government reports, stakeholder position papers, academic literature and media coverage to provide a broad understanding of South Africa's NHI policy and public discourse. Comparative case studies of universal health systems in similar settings, namely; Brazil, Thailand and Ghana offer insights into potential solutions for South Africa's unique challenges. Using thematic analysis supported by NVivo, the study identifies major themes, including financial sustainability, capacity constraints and stakeholder resistance. Findings show that the NHI has potential for achieving universal health coverage and addressing healthcare inequities in South Africa and similar socio-economic settings, significant issues, such as underfunding, inadequate infrastructure and limited private sector engagement are barriers to successful implementation. Comparative insights highlight the importance of sufficient budget, effective governance and continuous stakeholder consultation. The study concludes that, while South Africa demonstrates strong political commitment to universal health coverage, substantial reforms and strategic coordination are essential for achieving the NHI's goals, minimising unintended consequences, ensuring a balanced integration of public and private healthcare sectors.

Introduction

Background on the National Health Insurance (NHI) in South Africa

The National Health Insurance (NHI) scheme in South Africa is a large-scale and revolutionary attempt to redesign and enhance the healthcare sector in South Africa to promote Universal Health Coverage (UHC). Universal health coverage (UHC) means that all people have access to the full range of quality health services they need, when and where they need them, without financial hardship. It covers the full continuum of essential health services, from health promotion to prevention, treatment, rehabilitation, and palliative care across the life course [1]. Introduced in 2011, and incrementally implemented in recent years, the NHI has been designed to deal with the inequality in healthcare provision in post-apartheid South Africa [2]. Healthcare delivery in South Africa, as obtained from the South African healthcare system literature can be described as a bifurcated system, where only about 16% of the

population access the private healthcare delivery system with quality healthcare delivery and the remaining about 84% of the population accessing services through the public health delivery system which suffers from unavailability of resources and poor quality of services [3]. Key issues include the "quadruple burden" of HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, non-communicable diseases, and injuries, which together lead to high mortality and strain public health resources. The public health system, serving the 84% of the population, is underfunded, especially in rural areas, further perpetuating the divide created under the apartheid regime. The NHI aims to provide equitable, high-quality care by extending health insurance cover to all South citizens by establishment of a prescribed universal mandatory health insurance scheme that will make health services accessible to all citizens [4]. This is in line with the current worldwide call for Universal Health Coverage (UHC) which is part of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals,

More Information

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specifically Goal 3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages [5].

Nevertheless, the process of making transformative change and adoption of the NHI has not been smooth-sailing; it has elicited various discourses and controversies. The latest stage in this process is the signing of the second Presidential Health Compact in August 2024, which has been heavily criticised by important stakeholders in various fields, including medicine and business, stakeholders have apprehensions that NHI may exacerbate existing bureaucratic inefficiencies in the healthcare system rather than resolve them [6], [7] similarly raised the issue. This underlines the complexities of implementing such transformative change and the need for further consultation and collaboration to align NHI goals with sustainable health outcomes for all South Africans.

Rationale for the Study

South Africa's recent experience with its National Health Insurance (NHI) underscores these difficulties, particularly as a middle-income country marked by stark social and economic inequalities, which exacerbate the challenges of achieving universal health coverage [8]. The efforts to advance the development of a national health insurance system can be best understood and described as a policy option which is not just challenging; in fact, it is a set of challenges that arise every time a country engages in a process of designing, evaluating, and putting into practice a new system of financing healthcare with limited financial and human resources.

Because of the relatively recent events as pertains to the Presidential Health Compact and the on-going debate on the ability and effectiveness of the NHI policy – there is a lack of academic literature that discusses the policy evaluation process, engagement initiatives with players in the health sector, as well as the main and unique challenges of implementing this gigantic health reform. With the current state of healthcare policies in South Africa, this research proposes to fill this gap by undertaking an analytical assessment of the NHI policy on the basis of South Africa's wider health politics and its impact that may be occasioned by the policy on the two sectors of health care: the public and the private.

This research aims to contribute to advance the theoretical knowledge and understanding of Universal Health Coverage (UHC) in developing countries, particularly focusing on the unique challenges that arise when implementing such systems in contexts marked by significant inequality and critical resource constraints. By examining the South African experience, this study also seeks to draw on insights from other countries that have undergone similar transitions, aiming to extrapolate lessons that may benefit future efforts in comparable settings.

Objectives of the Paper

The primary objectives of this paper are discussed below.

- a. To critically analyse the policy formulation process of the NHI in South Africa, examining its evolution from initial proposal to the current implementation stage.
- b. To assess the extent to which the NHI aligns with South Africa's broader health goals and international commitments to universal health coverage.
- c. To examine the reactions and concerns of key stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, businesses, and civil society organisations, regarding the NHI implementation.
- d. To identify and analyse the main implementation challenges facing the NHI, including funding mechanisms, administrative structures, and potential impacts on existing healthcare systems.
- e. To explore the implications of stakeholder resistance, as exemplified by the boycott of the Presidential Health Compact, on the successful implementation of the NHI.
- f. To propose evidence-based recommendations for improving the NHI framework and implementation strategy to ensure its effectiveness in achieving universal health coverage in South Africa.

Research Questions

To guide this study, the following research questions have been formulated.

- a. How has the NHI policy in South Africa evolved since its initial proposal, and to what extent does it align with the country's broader health goals and international UHC commitments?
- b. What are the primary concerns and criticisms raised by key stakeholders regarding the NHI, and how have these shaped the policy discourse and implementation process?
- c. What are the main implementation challenges facing the NHI, particularly in terms of financing, administrative capacity, and integration with existing healthcare systems?
- d. How has stakeholder resistance, as evidenced by the boycott of the Presidential Health Compact, impacted the prospects for successful implementation of the NHI?
- e. What policy adjustments and stakeholder engagement strategies could be employed to address the current challenges and improve the likelihood of successful NHI implementation?

Literature Review

Overview of Universal Health Coverage (UHC) Globally
Achieving UHC has become a focal area of concern in the international health care agenda over the past decade. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines UHC as the idea that everyone should access essential,

quality health care without threatening their financial stability [1]. This idea has received much attention in recent years after being included as one of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals in 2015 as target 3.8: *Achieve universal health coverage, including financial risk protection, access to quality essential health-care services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all* [9].

Different health system reforms have been implemented around the world in pursuit of Universal Health Coverage; with countries apply different strategies depending on their societal environment, availability of resources and political situations. Some high-income countries, such as the United Kingdom, Canada, and Germany, have long-standing fully funded universal health care regimes, while many low and middle-income countries have made fairly good progress within the last few years [10].

Pilot examples of UHC implementation in developing countries include (1) Thailand which provides the Universal Coverage Scheme which altered coverage from the west to the entire country in 2002; (2) Rwanda that has offered the Community-Based Health Insurance Program that markedly enhanced population's access to healthcare. This has, in turn, dispelled myths and informed practice and strategies that have helped other nations, including South Africa in their journey to achieving UHC.

As noted by [11], these efforts are not without some challenges. Challenges include the capacity of numerous nations to finance UHC in order to offer good healthcare services fairly and efficiently, ensuring a transition from current health systems. The COVID-19 outbreak across the world has reaffirmed the need for strong and effective healthcare systems for all in parallel to stressing the healthcare systems globally [12].

Historical Context of NHI in South Africa

This paper identifies that coordinated, state-funded National Health Insurance (NHI) in South Africa has its origin in the struggle against apartheid and the subsequent endeavours to redress the historical injustices relating to equity of access and outcomes to health care. The ANC in its National Health Plan for the year 1994 for the first time presented the notion of a single national health system [3].

But the formal invention of the NHI policy was begun in the year 2007 after the African National Congress made a resolution at its National Conference in Polokwane, during the 52nd session of the conference. This resolution required a rollout of a National Health Insurance system that was aimed at eradicating inequity within the health sector [7]. Ghana introduced the idea of implementing NHI in the form of its National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) in 2003, the

government began with the publishing of the Green Paper and the White Paper on NHI in the years 2011 and 2015 respectively [2]. By 2016, the NHIS was already well-established, although facing significant challenges related to funding, political interference, and operational inefficiencies.

This paper aims to take a look at the evolution of the healthcare sector in South Africa and observe that history narrates a story of apartheid that has for long featured in the systematic differences between the black and white communities. Efforts to counter such disparities have ranged from scale-up of primary health care, provision of free health care to pregnant women and children, and wide-ranging health camps. That is, previous attempts at integrating public and private sectors have been inadequate in closing the divide in health care quality and availability.

The NHI proposal is the most comprehensive and far-reaching effort made to date to alter the character of South Africa's health system [13]. [4] argues that the NHI presents a pivotal opportunity for South Africa to adopt effective models from other countries of similar contexts, enhance collaboration between government and non-state actors, and ultimately advance health equity. The author states that by recognising and nurturing grassroots innovations like the Transnet Phelophepa Health Trains - mobile clinics that use South Africa's railway network to provide essential healthcare services, reaching over 200 000 patients annually in remote communities, through such, South Africa can leverage its strengths to address existing health disparities and develop sustainable solutions for its diverse population.

Policy Framework Governing NHI

Currently, the historical development of the policy framework for South African NHI looks like this. The key policy documents that have shaped the NHI are discussed below.

- a. The Green Paper on NHI (2011): From this document, the initial concept of NHI was explained and it was suggested that the implementation of the scheme would take place in phases, planned to extend up to 14 years (Department of Health, 2011).
- b. The White Paper on NHI (2015): This paper offered further specifics on how to institute NHI, funding structures and service provision frameworks (Department of Health, 2017).
- c. The NHI Bill (2019): This bill was launched in Parliament in August 2019 and if passed into law, would provide the legal basis for the implementation of NHI [14].

The NHI policy framework aims to create a system that would allow the payment for affordable, quality, competent health services for all South Africans according to their health status and not their ability to

pay [15]. The following are the key features of the proposed NHI system.

- a. Universal coverage for all legal residents
- b. Comprehensive service benefits
- c. Free Services at the point of care
- d. Mandatory prepayment of health care, distinct from out-of-pocket payments
- e. A single fund to pool resources and purchase services

The policy framework also describes a gradual approach to implementation, with the first phase (2012-2017) including the start-up activities for the main components of the NHI, the second phase (2017-2022) including the development and implementation of NHI legislation and the third phase (2022-2026) with the introduction of compulsory prepayments [3].

[16] conducted an evaluation of the NHI between 2017 and 2018 which aligns with the transition from Phase 1 to Phase 2. It assessed the progress and challenges faced during the implementation, particularly during the early years of the second phase. In their evaluation, the authors highlight successes and barriers encountered in the implementation of various components of the NHI, including data quality issues and the lack of effective coverage indicators, which hinder accurate progress assessment. However, notable successes included increased population coverage of health services and improvements in health information systems, which reflects the ongoing efforts to transition into Phase 2 activities (development and implementation of legislation).

Stakeholder Responses and Criticism

The NHI proposal has elicited varied reactions across segments of the South African health sector. While supporters and detractors concur on the necessity to address health disparities and inequalities, they find the strategies proposed under the NHI to be problematic.

The many stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, have posed questions on working conditions, remuneration, and autonomy that could be affected by the changes. According to a study done by [8], the doctors interviewed expressed understanding and support of UHC but questioned whether the government can successfully execute and oversee the NHI.

Medical schemes and private hospitals have on their part expressed their concerns in their role within the NHI arrangements. Some claimed that the NHI would most likely result in job losses in private sector and a decline in the overall quality of the health services [17]. According to the [72], the NHI might bring adverse economic repercussions that could potentially lower the standing of South Africa's credit rating, as [18] pointed out.

Civil Society Organisations have largely welcomed the general fascism of the NHI but expressed concern about the execution plan and recommended an increase in public engagement in policy-making processes [19].

Scholars and policy researchers have extensively discussed the details of the NHI option, including its viability, effects on the quality of health care, and additional social factors about health. According to [20], the NHI, if well implemented, can help to reduce health inequity, but the process will have underlying determining factors of socioeconomic inequalities.

Comparative Analysis of Similar Health Systems

It would be helpful for understanding South Africa's NHI proposal to look at a number of middle-income country health system reforms. Three relevant case studies can be distinguished, namely Brazil's Unified Health System (SUS), Thailand's Universal Coverage Scheme (UCS) and Ghana's National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS). SUS in Brazil, which started in 1988, is designed to deliver outfit health care with governmental funding but decentralised. However, advances derived from SUS have positively transformed the health of this population and social disparities [21]. Some of the lessons learnt in Brazil are commitment at the political hand's level, decentralisation, and people participation. Thailand implemented UCS in 2002 and attained universal coverage in the first-year of implementation. The scheme is funded through general taxation; it has achieved its goal of increasing healthcare and financial risk protection [9]. The case of Thailand shows that strategic purchasing, proper strengthening of the primary care level, and resource management played great roles. The GHC was established in 2003 through the passage of the National Health Insurance Act to help achieve the NHIS goal to afford the residents an affordable health care. Despite comprising and expanding access to health care services the scheme has some barrier to achieving universal health coverage and financial viability. Ghana's experience shows the challenges of the scheme in essentially a developing country hence calls for adequate financing for the NHIS. A comparison of these systems to South Africa's proposal of NHI show that there are both similarities and differences. As it is the case with Brazil and Thailand, South Africa plans its single system to be funded by the state. However, that perception does not sit well with South Africa because, because of inequality in health care provision and the extent to which the private sector dominates the South African health sector [22].

The experiences of these countries offer valuable lessons for South Africa, as summarised below.

- a. The importance of political will and sustained commitment to UHC
- b. The need for careful planning and phased implementation

- c. The critical role of strong primary healthcare systems
- d. The challenges of integrating existing health systems and managing stakeholder interests
- e. The importance of sustainable financing mechanisms

Such comparative findings can be useful to South Africa, highlighting some challenges that may be realised and the strategies that are likely to be effective in dealing with such challenges.

Consequently, this literature review has aimed at giving a background of UHC across the world, describing the history and policy landscape of the proposed NHI in South Africa, reviewing the judgments and critiques of the stakeholders, and comparing the NHI idea to similar structural changes in other middle-income nations. This paper lays the groundwork for further discussion of the difficulties and opportunities of NHI implementation in South Africa.

Methodology

Research Design

This research utilises a qualitative research design to achieve an in-depth understanding of the NHI policy formulation, stakeholder management, and implementation challenges in South Africa. The qualitative approach allows for the exploration of the socio-political and economic dynamics that may have shaped or hindered the implementation of the NHI in South Africa [23].

Specific qualitative methodologies, including case study research and grounded theory are employed to gather rich insights into stakeholder experiences and the contextual factors influencing the NHI [24,25].

The theoretical frameworks guiding this study include health policy analysis frameworks, which provides a structure for examining policy formulation and implementation challenges [26], stakeholder theory to analyse the roles and influences of various stakeholders in the NHI implementation process [27], and implementation science to understand the barriers and facilitators affecting the successful uptake of health policies [28]. Together, these methodologies and frameworks align with the research questions identified in the introduction [29].

The study is structured in three main phases as listed below.

- a. Document analysis and literature review
- b. Comparative analysis with similar health system reforms in other countries

This approach enables triangulation of data collected from various sources, enhancing the credibility and dependability of the results [24]. Triangulation allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the NHI policy by cross-referencing data from documents, literature, and case study contexts, thereby strengthening the robustness of the findings [30]. Yin

argues that triangulation helps to corroborate the same phenomenon from different angles, thus adding rigor to the case study methodology, this paper uses data, theoretical and methodological triangulation to reinforce the reliability and depth of the research.

Data Collection Methods

Document Analysis

The basis of this study is a critical analysis of all the related documents. The types of documents included in the analysis are listed below.

- a. Policy documents: This includes the NHI Green Paper (2011), NHI White Paper (2015), NHI Bill (2019), as well as any subsequent amendment or policy brief that was released on the matter.
- b. Government reports: Annual reports, National Health Council minutes, and parliamentary committee reports of the Department of Health.
- c. Stakeholder position papers: These can include submissions from medical professionals associations, trade unions, chambers of commerce and civil society organisations.
- d. Academic literature: Current peer-reviewed scholarly articles journals, books, and conferences on NHI and UHC in South Africa and other countries.
- e. Media reports: Newspaper and magazine articles, press releases and blogs referring to NHI evolution and controversies.

The documents are analysed in accordance with the systematic review methodology that was described by [31], which consists of skimming, reading, and interpreting the documents.

Comparative Case Studies

In order to understand the relevance and applicability of the terminologies used and the lessons that could be deduced for South Africa's NHI, comparative case studies of other similar health system reforms in other middle-income countries are also performed. The cases selected for analysis are listed below.

- a. Brazil's Unified Health System or Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS)
- b. Universal Health Coverage in Thailand is in the form of Universal Coverage Scheme (UCS)
- c. The National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) of Ghana

These purposefully chosen cases are relevant based on their similarities to the South African context and the availability of English-language documentation. This component of the study uses document analysis to examine policy papers, evaluation reports, and academic literature on each of these health systems, allowing for a deeper understanding of their structures, challenges, and outcomes.

Data Analysis

The qualitative data from document analysis are examined using thematic analysis, following the six-step process outlined by [32]. This process is supported

by NVivo software to aid in coding and organisation. The coding process is both deductive, with codes derived from the research questions and theoretical framework, and inductive, allowing new themes to emerge naturally from the data [33].

Comparative Analysis

The case studies are compared using a framework by [34] meant for the analysis of health care systems. This framework considers the following elements.

- a. Financing mechanisms
- b. Service provision
- c. Organisational structure
- d. Regulation and governance

The implementation section of the analysis examines the implementation plan of the proposed NHI in South Africa in relation to the barriers and solutions arising from Brazil, Thailand, and Ghana's systems.

Ethical Considerations

This research adheres to ethical practices to ensure integrity and respect throughout the study. The ethical considerations are as follows:

- a. **Data Integrity:** All documents are carefully vetted for credibility, authenticity, and relevance. Any documents that may contain sensitive information are handled according to ethical guidelines to avoid misuse or misrepresentation of data.
- b. **Data Protection:** All data, including documents and analytical notes, are stored securely on password-protected devices and encrypted cloud storage systems, accessible only to the research team. This measure helps safeguard sensitive information and upholds ethical standards in document management.
- c. **Ethical approval:** This study exclusively uses publicly available documents, such as policy papers, government reports, and academic publications. Since no human participants or confidential information are involved, formal ethical approval was not required. However, the research adheres to ethical standards by ensuring accurate representation of information, respecting intellectual property rights, and maintaining the integrity of the data analysis process.
- d. **Researcher reflexivity:** Several of the members of the research team continue to reflect on their positionality and possible bias while conducting the study [35].
- e. **Dissemination of findings:** An assurance is given to disseminate the research outcomes with the participants and stakeholders of the study through published articles in open access journals and policy briefs.

Through this comprehensive method of data collection and analysis, the study will offer a detailed understanding of the South Africa NHI policy, the problems surrounding implementation, and recommend solutions. Such an approach enables the undertaking of an extensive investigation into the

multiple factors involved in the prospect of enacting NHI in the different countries involved in the study.

Policy Formulation and the NHI

Development of the NHI Policy

The process of formulating and implementing the South African NHI policy has not been an easy and short one but a long process ever since the creation of a post-apartheid South Africa. This policy direction of the NHI can be traced to the African National Congress' (ANC) 1994 National Health Plan which laid down a future plan of a single national health system [3]. However, the formation of policy in South Africa started after the ANC elective conference held in Polokwane in 2007 where the party resolved to implement an NHI system for equity and efficiency in the unit [7].

The policy formulation process has been characterised by the following key phases.

- a. **Green Paper (2011):** This document painted a picture of how NHI was to be implemented through a phased implementation plan spread over fourteen years. It was based on the values of universal healthcare insurance provision and fairness or solidarity [36].
- b. **White Paper (2015):** This Green paper was followed by this document, which presented further specific proposals for the financing, organisation and operation, as well as the governance of NHI [37].
- c. **NHI Bill (2019):** Presented to the Parliament in August 2019, this bill seeks to provide the legal framework for the realisation of NHI and among them is the establishment of the NHI Fund as the single source buyer of the health services [38].
- d. **Ongoing revisions and amendments:** The policy remains dynamic in order to respond to feedback from its stakeholders, challenges associated with its application, and shifts in political and economic environments [39].

During this process, the following have shaped policy formulation: The global move towards the provision of Universal Health Coverage; internal politics; and the ever-increasing shortcomings in South Africa's health system, especially in relation to inequality and inefficiency [2].

Key Policy Components

The NHI policy, as it has evolved through various iterations, encompasses several key components which are discussed below.

- a. **Universal Coverage:** It is important to note that the NHI seeks to make efficient quality health services accessible to every citizen of South Africa irrespective of their financial status. This refers to both the native individuals of South Africa as well as the international legal residents [5].
- b. **Comprehensive Benefits Package:** The policy seeks to implement a well-coordinated bundle of healthcare services: the first, second, and third levels.

These are includes the preventive, promotive, curative, and rehabilitative services.

c. **Single Payer System:**The NHI Fund is proposed here as a single public fund established at the central level to pay for health services for the entire population. This is quite an important shift from the current trend where research is funded by both public and private actors with diversified and complex systems [3].

d. **Mandatory Prepayment:** The policy put forward a model of compulsory preliminary payment, which is different from charges made at the time of service provision. This is aimed at increasing equity and financial risk protection as espoused in [5].

e. **Strategic Purchasing:** The NHI Fund is expected to be a strategic purchaser, entering into contracts with both state-owned and private healthcare suppliers depending on their needs and performance [40].

f. **Gatekeeping and Referral System:** The policy also focuses on the essential package of care and advocates for a system of the first-contact and access to specialist care in the most appropriate manner [8].

g. **Quality Improvement:** Some of the policy interventions that the NHI policy entails to enhance the quality of health care services are the creation of an Office of Health Standards Compliance according to [2].

Legal Framework and NHI Act

The legal foundation of the NHI is chiefly provided by means of the NHI Bill, which was presented in Parliament in 2019. The bill seeks to afford recognition to the right to all health care services in terms of section 27 of the constitution of the republic of South Africa [41,42].

The key provisions of the NHI Bill are listed below.

a. **Creation of the NHI Fund as an independent state body**

b. **Explanation of the population within which NHI is defined**

c. **Description of the elements of the nominated benefits package and coverage of conditions of service**

d. **Specifications involving accreditation of healthcare providers**

e. **Structures of governance for the NHI Fund, society: With reference to the Minister of Health**

f. **Funding models, including the NHI tax that has been under discussion**

The bill has gone through all the consultation periods among the public and in the parliament. This bill has been met with criticisms regarding its legal compliance particularly on the part of the provincial health department as well as the seemingly imposing restrictions that impede consumer sovereignty [43].

The legal regulation of NHI also relates to other health legislation, the National Health Act of 2003 and the Medical Schemes Act of 1998.

Alignment with South Africa's Health Goals

The NHI policy is well anchored with the country's health priorities as enshrined in the National Development Plan 2030 and other policy frameworks. These goals are listed below.

a. **Reducing inequality in access to healthcare**

b. **Improving the quality of health services**

c. **Reducing the burden of disease, particularly HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and non-communicable diseases**

d. **Strengthening the health system, especially at the primary care level**

e. **Improving health outcomes and life expectancy**

The NHI is regarded as the mechanism that can help to reach these goals because it is able to eliminate the inherent unfairness of the existing structure of the health care. Its purpose is to help to make the choice among goods and services more rational, to promote cross subsidisation between the rich and the poor, and between the healthy and the sick and, thus, to make the health system of the country more efficient and equitable [22].

Despite this, there are scholars who have raised an eyebrow about the ability of the NHI as formulated at the moment in delivering on these health objectives. Some issues that have been raised include issues of practicability or practicality, on whether there will be side effects and issues to do with the roles of structural socio-economic transformation in order to deal with the social determinants of health [3,7].

Further, the direction of the NHI in relation to the economic objectives of South Africa has raised debate. On the positive side, as discussed by advocates of NHI, enhanced population health will lead to economic growth and development, while critics pointed out negative economic effects of proposed NHI funding cells [18].

The COVID-19 crisis has injected new life into this discourse by revealing both a desperate need for a better and fair healthcare system and the economic realities of funding such a system during a depression [19].

In conclusion, much of the formulation process of South Africa's NHI has been rather difficult and largely characterised by a lot of tension and disagreement due to compelling dynamics of implementing UHC in a considerably unequal society. However, there are still some serious concerns regarding its applicability and effects on South Africa's health policy agenda. Since this policy is still relatively young, there is a need to carry out more comprehensive research and engage other stakeholders as the policy proceeds in order to help adapt the NHI framework accordingly and optimally so that the goal of attaining universal health coverage in South Africa can be achieved.

Stakeholder Engagement and Reactions

Overview of Key Stakeholders

The implementation of the NHI in South Africa requires the engagement of different stakeholders who have their own agendas, issues of concern, and power weavers. Studying these stakeholders and their positions is fundamental when measuring the possibilities and barriers to NHI implementation. The key stakeholder groups are listed below.

- a. Government: Including the Department of Health, National Treasury, and other relevant ministries
- b. Healthcare Professionals: Doctors, nurses, and allied health professionals
- c. Private Sector: Medical schemes, private hospitals, and pharmaceutical companies
- d. Civil Society: Patient advocacy groups, labor unions, and community organisations
- e. International Organisations: World Health Organization (WHO), World Bank, and other development partners
- f. Academia: Health policy researchers and economists

All these groups have contributed to the formation of the NHI policy, the process of refining and implementing this policy [2].

Stakeholder Criticisms of the NHI

Although there is consensus that measures need to be taken to eradicate healthcare disparities in South Africa in particular, a number of elements suggested under the NHI have been the subject of numerous discussions and criticism.

Healthcare Professionals

The following are the responses from the different professions in the healthcare sector to the NHI. A preparatory survey for the NHI by [13] revealed the fact that despite the majority of doctors endorsing the concepts of UHC, they had severe doubts about the capacity of the government to implement efficient NHI management. The main concerns are listed below:

- a. Potential negative impacts on working conditions and remuneration
- b. Fears of increased bureaucracy and reduced professional autonomy
- c. Doubts about the capacity of the public health system to deliver quality care under NHI
- d. Concerns about the role of private practice within the NHI framework

The South African Medical Association (SAMA) has criticised the lack of consultation with healthcare professionals regarding the policies and raised concern as to how the NHI would impact practicing medicine [44].

Private Sector

The proponents of NHI have also been receiving criticism from opposing parties most especially from

the private health sector, the medical schemes and private. Their main concerns are listed below:

- a. Potential job losses in the private sector
- b. Fears of a reduction in healthcare quality and choice
- c. Questions about the financial sustainability of the NHI model
- d. Concerns about the future role of private health insurance

For their part, the Board of Healthcare Funders (BHF) [73,74] which represents medical schemes has predicted that the NHI could result in significant decline in the size of the private healthcare sector in South Africa, with the potential to wreak havoc across the whole health system [17].

Civil Society

Major stakeholders in civil society have largely backed objectives underpinning the NHI but has called for deeper implementation strategies and call for increased public participation. The key issues are listed below.

- a. Calls for more transparent and inclusive policy development processes
- b. Emphasis on addressing social determinants of health alongside healthcare reform
- c. Concerns about potential corruption and mismanagement of NHI funds
- d. Advocacy for stronger accountability mechanisms in NHI implementation

For instance, The Treatment Action Campaign (TAC), an influential HIV/AIDS organisation has urged the NHI to address the presently existing differences of service delivery in terms of the needs of the disadvantaged groups [45].

Academia and Policy Analysts

Analysts in both academia and policy have done their critiqued various components of the NHI, especially its financial sustainability, effect on quality of care, and capacity to meet social determinants factors. The key critiques are listed below:

- a. Questions about the fiscal space for NHI implementation, especially given South Africa's economic challenges [3]
- b. Concerns about the capacity of the state to manage a complex health financing system [7]
- c. Debates about the appropriate balance between public and private sector involvement in NHI [22]
- d. Calls for more rigorous evidence-based policy making in NHI development [20].

Impact of Stakeholder Boycotts

The latest development to be seen as a challenge to the implementation of NHI is the recent boycott of the Presidential Health Compact by physicians' federations and business coalitions. The boycott has had several impacts which are discussed below.

a. **Diminished Legitimacy:** This lack of representation from the key actors in the signing of the compact means that the validity and the representativeness of the NHI policy formulation have been a lot of questions [46,47].

b. **Implementation Challenges:** The absence of 'ownership' of important players in the sphere of healthcare delivery and financing may constitute serious challenges to the delivery of the promising NHI agenda [48].

c. **Public Perception:** Social tension created by the boycott has led to uncertainty about the NHI and demoralisation of policy support [49,50].

d. **Policy Refinement:** This development has pointed to the need for an ongoing engagement forum involving the various stakeholders and possibly adjustment of the aspects in the NHI policy that is worrisome to the public [51,52].

Government's Response to Stakeholder Concerns

The South African government has attempted to address stakeholder concerns through various mechanisms as discussed below.

a. **Public Consultations:** The Department of Health has held briefing sessions throughout the country on the NHI Bill such as parliamentary proceedings and business meetings [53].

b. **Stakeholder Engagement Forums:** The general formation of several avenues of stakeholder engagement, for example, the National Health Insurance Work Streams to receive contribution from other sectors [54,55].

c. **Policy Adjustments:** certain amendments have been made in a bid to reflect stakeholder's opinions with specifics on what the private healthcare providers and medical scheme have to do within a policy component of NHI policy [56,57].

d. **Communication Campaigns:** Maladministration has ensured the government starts public communication campaigns to clear misconceptions of the NHI and rally support [58].

e. **Phased Implementation:** The phased implementation approach in that one can continuously fine-tune and adapt the variation of the NHI model that is deemed suitable in the response to the voices of various constituents and implementation experiences [59].

Nevertheless, many obstacles lie in the path to achieving stakeholder management and balancing the various and, quite often, conflicting needs. It remains to be seen how the government can first create the necessary positive sentiment and then deal with the key issues concerning the NHI implementation.

So far, the stakeholder engagement of South Africa's NHI has been marked with strong support for the concept of UHC, coupled with growing concern with specific policy instruments. Recent boycotts by

stakeholders socialise the fact that reaching a consensus as to the feasibility of the NHI model remains a daunting task.

Consequently, stakeholder engagement is expected to play a central role in the success of the NHI in the future. This will require the following elements:

a. More inclusive and transparent policy development processes

b. Greater efforts to address the specific concerns of key stakeholder groups

c. Ongoing mechanisms for stakeholder input and feedback throughout the implementation process

d. Clear communication about the benefits and challenges of NHI implementation

e. Flexibility in policy design to accommodate diverse stakeholder interests while maintaining the core principles of universal health coverage

While the South African government moves forward with the process of fine-tuning and putting into practice the initiative toward the institutionalisation of the NHI policy, the process of managing and mediating these multiple and often competing stakeholder concerns, all the while keeping the overarching goal of achieving equitable access to quality health care for everybody in the country in view, will remain a key issue.

Implementation Challenges

Barriers to implementing the National Health Insurance (NHI) in South Africa are multifaceted. They cut across capital, service delivery, management, governance, as well as stakeholder issues. It is therefore important to understand these challenges in order to come up with the appropriate interventions to counter them and make the NHI implementation successful.

Funding and Financial Sustainability

[60,61] note that the biggest problem that the NHI faces is how to fund it especially when the country is grappling with problems of a fragile economy which has resulted in budget cuts across all levels of government and departments.

Funding Mechanisms

The sources of funding for the NHI have been a topic of discussion for a long time, and here are the most viable ones; the NHI Bill proposes the use of general tax revenues, payroll taxes and a levy on personal income tax [14]. The following concerns have been raised:

a. The feasibility of increasing the tax burden in a struggling economy with high unemployment rates [3]

b. The potential impact on business competitiveness and job creation [18]

c. The adequacy of the proposed funding to cover the comprehensive benefits package envisioned under the NHI [22]

Economic Context

Barriers to NHI implementation in South Africa include economic difficulties which have been caused by the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. Low economic

growth, high national debt, and repeated credit rating downgrades strain the fiscus, limiting capacity for extensive health system reforms [62]. Here, the National Treasury has raised questions on the sustainability of the NHI courtesy of these constraints within the Kenyan economy [63].

Cost Control Measures

Cost control in the NHI system will be significant due to which more effective measures will need to be integrated. These measures are discussed below:

- a. Developing robust systems for strategic purchasing of health services [40]
- b. Implementing effective gatekeeping and referral systems to ensure appropriate utilisation of services [8]
- c. Managing the costs of pharmaceuticals and medical technologies [64]

Coverage and Accessibility Issues

Ensuring equitable access to quality healthcare services under the NHI presents the following challenges.

Geographic Disparities

Historical spatial patterns in South Africa create some of the-limiting factors in addressing the issue of universal health coverage. More so emerging challenges that affect delivery of healthcare services include inadequacy of health facilities and human resource especially in rural settings [65]. Addressing these geographic disparities will require the following measures:

- a. Significant investment in healthcare infrastructure in underserved areas
- b. Innovative strategies for attracting and retaining healthcare workers in rural and remote locations
- c. Leveraging technology, such as telemedicine, to improve access in hard-to-reach areas [66].

Human Resources for Health

Currently there is shortage of healthcare professionals especially in the public sector, this is an issue in the implementation of NHI. Some of the critical issues are discussed below.

- a. Inadequate production and retention of healthcare workers [67]
- b. Maldistribution of healthcare professionals between urban and rural areas, and between public and private sectors [13]
- c. The need for retraining and reskilling of healthcare workers to align with the NHI model of care [2]

Quality of Care

Ensuring that the quality of the delivery of the services in the context of the NHI is enhanced and preserved is of utmost importance. The challenges are discussed below.

- a. Addressing the current quality deficits in many public health facilities [65]

- b. Implementing effective quality assurance and improvement mechanisms across both public and private providers [2]

- c. Managing public expectations and perceptions of healthcare quality under the NHI [15]

Administrative and Operational Hurdles

The operational complexity of implementing a single-payer health system in South Africa presents the following significant administrative challenges.

Information Systems and Technology

Developing and implementing robust health information systems is crucial for the effective functioning of the NHI. Some of the challenges are listed below:

- a. Integrating diverse existing health information systems across public and private sectors [68]
- b. Ensuring data security and patient privacy in line with the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) [69,70]
- c. Building capacity for data management and analysis to support evidence-based decision-making within the NHI [56,68,70]

Governance and Management Capacity

In order for the NHI to be successful, there will need to be profound improvements in health system governance and management capacity. The improvements are discussed below:

- a. Developing effective governance structures for the NHI Fund that ensure transparency, accountability, and efficient resource allocation [19]
- b. Building management capacity at all levels of the health system to handle the increased administrative demands of the NHI [7]
- c. Addressing issues of corruption and mismanagement that have plagued the public health sector [67]

Provider Payment Mechanisms

Designing and implementing effective provider payment mechanisms under the NHI is crucial for controlling costs and incentivising quality care. The challenges identified are discussed as follows:

- a. Developing fair and efficient payment systems for different types of healthcare providers [40]
- b. Balancing the need for cost control with the imperative to maintain quality of care [5]
- c. Managing the transition from current payment systems to NHI payment mechanisms [15]

Implications of the Health Compact Boycott

The recent boycott of the Presidential Health Compact by key stakeholders has the following significant implications for NHI implementation:

Stakeholder Buy-in

As pointed out by the boycott, actively gaining buy in from key stakeholders, healthcare professionals and the private sector, is still a challenge [46]. The lack of

consensus in the NHI could slow good implementation and may erode public confidence in the NHI.

Policy Refinement

The boycott signifies the press for improved policy refinement to accommodate concerns from stakeholders. This could mean revisiting the design of the NHI [51].

Communication and Engagement

The boycott further reveals weaknesses in the government's communication with the stakeholders. Enhancing these will be significant for creating the general support required for implementing NHI [49].

Potential Impact on Public and Private Healthcare Sectors

The implementation of the NHI is expected to have significant impacts on both the public and private healthcare sectors, as discussed below.

Public Sector

In the public sector, the following are the key challenges:

- a. Upgrading infrastructure and quality of care to meet NHI standards [65]
- b. Managing the transition from the current system to the NHI, including changes in funding flows and accountability structures [19]
- c. Addressing existing inefficiencies and capacity constraints in public health facilities [67]

Private Sector

For the private sector, the following are some of the significant concerns:

- a. The future role of private health insurance and medical schemes under the NHI [17]
- b. Potential job losses and market contraction in the private healthcare industry [18]
- c. Adapting to new contracting and payment mechanisms under the NHI [39]

The core challenge to the establishment of the NHI in South Africa is the framework of issues that will surround the financial management of the idea and the available human resources, as well as other operational issues and resistance to change by other key players. Mitigating these challenges will require a sustained political will, policy innovations and good stakeholder management.

Discussion

National Health Insurance is a deliberate effort to tackle historical injustices in the South African health system. However, based on the analysis made in the preceding sections, it can be said that there are many intertwined issues when it comes to achieving the UHC through the NHI. In this discussion, the author will seek to bring together the major points of analysis that have been arrived at in this paper as well as examine their implications for the progression of healthcare reforms in South Africa in the future.

Analysis of Policy Implementation Gaps

Based on the review undertaken, a few important gaps between the ambitious goals of the NHI policy and the realities of its implementation are seen below.

Funding and Fiscal Space

First is the incongruence of the full benefits package proposed under NHI with fiscal reality in the economy. In fact, [19] and [5] observe that there is serious concern about the sustainability of the proposed funding mechanisms, particularly in light of South Africa's economic challenges and high unemployment rates.

This has been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has further squeezed the fiscal space for implementing the NHI [62]. This raises doubt over the likelihood of a full rollout of the NHI in the near to medium future, and forms an argument for a more incremental approach in line with fiscal realities.

Health System Capacity

Another big gap is the current ability of the health system to realise the aspirations of NHI. Indeed, [65] and [67] point out there are major deficits in the areas of infrastructure, human resources, and quality of care in the public sector. Closing these gaps will take much more investment and time than is envisaged for the realisation of the aspirations of NHI.

Further, maldistribution between urban and rural areas and between the public and private sectors is one of the major challenges to achieve equity in access for the NHI [13]. Such entrenched inequities would require innovative strategies to combat them.

Stakeholder Alignment

The recent boycott of the Presidential Health Compact by key stakeholders was a critical consensus-building gap and gap in stakeholder alignment [46]. The success of NHI would require high consensus-buying into and cooperation on the part of health care providers, the private sector, and civil society. The absence of any current alignment creates a serious implementation risk.

The Role of Political Will and Governance in NHI Success

The implementation of a reform as far-reaching as the NHI takes firm political will and good governance. The analysis indicates that even though there is unequivocal political dedication to the principle of universal health cover, its realisation in real life is not easy.

Policy Consistency and Long-term Vision

There is uncertainty amongst the stakeholders created by successive drafts and amendments which characterises the protracted NHI policy development process [39]. The need for greater coherence of the policy, informed by a well-considered and long-term perspective, would also be resilient to the changes in the political leadership.

Governance Capacity

As highlighted by [3] and [7], there are concerns about the governance capacity needed to manage a complex system like the NHI. For NHI to work, strengthening of the governance structures, enhancing transparency, and management capacity at every level of the health system will become imperative.

Intergovernmental Coordination

The effective implementation of NHI necessitates coordination within the national, provincial, and local government levels. Current challenges with regard to intergovernmental relations and the devolution of health services are threatening the smooth implementation of the NHI [7].

Potential Unintended Consequences

As commendable as the redress of health inequities may be, the analysis identifies several potential unintended consequences of the NHI that policymakers should be aware of including the following.

Private Sector Disruption

These changes may cause significant disruption in the private healthcare sector, including loss of jobs and a possible 'brain drain' in professions involving health care, as [17] and [18] warned.

Quality of Care Concerns

There are fears that in the rush to achieve this coverage, there may be levelling down of the quality in healthcare, especially because the public sector is not strong enough in advance of the implementation of the NHI [65].

Fiscal Pressure

If anything, the NHI might crowd out other important social spending in the limited fiscal space available to the South African government [71]. This could have broader implications for social development and reducing inequality.

Future Prospects for the NHI

Despite the many challenges noted above, the NHI represents a critical opportunity to transform South Africa's health system and deal with historical inequities. The future prospects for the NHI are based on several variables as discussed below.

Adaptive Policy Making

Health system reform is intricate; hence, the implementation of NHI requires an adaptive approach. It will entail constant learning, flexibility in policy adjustment in light of experiences that may emerge during implementation, and openness to alternative models that may be available [20].

Strengthening the Foundation

Health system strengthening, through targeted investments at the level of primary health care and in underserved areas, will become crucial to providing a solid foundation for the success of NHI implementation [8].

Stakeholder Engagement

Engagement thrusts on NHI at all levels need improvement so that wider consensus may be obtained. This may require reassessment of some elements in the design of the NHI as part of addressing some of the key concerns of stakeholders themselves [51].

Leveraging Technology

Adoption of such technological innovations as e-health and telemedicine could contribute to solving the access and efficiency problem of NHI [66].

In this light, it becomes clear that the NHI does indeed face significant implementation challenges but still represents one of the most integral policy interventions in efforts to reduce inequalities in access to health services within the South African context. Any prospects for advancing this ambitious health reform will need to achieve a delicate balance among the need to resolve issues of funding constraints, health system capacity, and various concerns raised by a wide range of stakeholders while sustaining the critical policy principle of universal health coverage.

Recommendations

Drawing from the foregoing analysis of policy formulation and stakeholder engagement, as well as the challenges of implementation regarding the NHI in South Africa, the following recommendations can be advanced to make this ambitious health reform more effective and implementable.

Policy Adjustments for Effective Implementation

1. Phased Implementation Approach: Adopt a more graduated, phased approach in the implementation of the NHI, this should be aligned to fiscal realities and health system capacity. This may take the following forms.
 - a. Accelerating the availability of essential health services in poor areas
 - b. Progressive expansion of the benefit package to the creation of fiscal space
 - c. The piloting of major components of the NHI before scale-up
2. Flexible Financing Mechanisms: Develop a more diversified and flexible financing strategy and targeting.
 - a. Considering innovative funding sources other than traditional taxation, including sin taxes or public-private partnerships
 - b. Allowing for adjustments based on economic conditions and progress at implementation
 - c. Incorporates measures for risk mitigation to make sure of fiscal sustainability
3. Strengthen Primary Health Care: Payment of greater attention to strengthening primary health care as the foundation of NHI.
 - a. Invest more in the community-based teams of health workers and infrastructure for primary care

- b. Include comprehensive, preventive, and promotive health services into the NHI benefits package
 - c. Robust referral systems for appropriate utilisation of services
4. Role of Private Sector: Clearly articulate the role of private health providers and medical schemes within the framework of NHI.
- a. Well-defined pathways through which the private sector can contribute to service delivery
 - b. Transitional provisions that would allow for medical schemes to transition toward the NHI environment
 - c. Incentives to attract investment by the private sector in under-resourced areas

Strategies for Re-engaging Stakeholders

1. Inclusive Policy Dialogue: Establish regular, systematic mechanisms for inclusive policy consultation that delivers the following.
- a. Engage all stakeholders, including those that pulled out of the Health Compact
 - b. Provide opportunities for active input into refining policy and planning for implementation
 - c. Allow openness in decision-making
2. Targeted Stakeholder Engagement: Determine ways to engage targeted stakeholders around their individual sets of issues to be considered.
- a. Health professionals: Salary matters, working conditions, and professional independence
 - b. Private sector: Assure them of no disruption to market and describe opportunities for collaboration
 - c. Civil Society: Describe mechanisms for community participation and accountability
3. Communication and Education Campaign: Engage in an effective public communication and education campaign in order to achieve the following.
- a. Dispels misunderstandings about NHI
 - b. Promote possible benefits on account of different population groups
 - c. Manage public expectations about how and at what pace improvements will be effected
4. Collaborative Problem-Solving: Establish joint working groups with key stakeholders to achieve the following.
- a. Address specific implementation challenges
 - b. Develop workable solutions that balance diverse interest
 - c. Foster a sense of shared ownership in the NHI's success

Enhancing Collaboration Between Public and Private Sectors

1. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Develop a framework for strategic PPPs that might achieve the following.
- a. Leverage private sector expertise and resources to strengthen public health infrastructure

- b. Explore innovative service delivery models that combine public funding with private provision
 - c. Ensure clear governance structures and accountability mechanisms for PPPs
2. Capacity Building Programs: Implement joint capacity building programs that will attain the following.
- a. Facilitate knowledge and skills transfer between public and private sectors
 - b. Focus on areas such as health system management, quality improvement, and health informatics
 - c. Promote a culture of collaboration and shared learning
3. Integrated Health Information Systems: Develop integrated health information systems that will enable the following.
- a. Enable seamless data sharing between public and private providers
 - b. Support continuity of care across different levels of the health system
 - c. Ensure patient privacy and data security in line with regulations
4. Quality Improvement Initiatives: Launch collaborative quality improvement initiatives that achieve the following objectives.
- a. Establish common quality standards across public and private providers
 - b. Implement peer review and learning mechanisms
 - c. Recognise and reward high-performing facilities across both sectors

Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms

1. Comprehensive Monitoring and Evaluation Framework: Develop a robust monitoring and evaluation framework that will achieve the following.
- a. Tracks progress against clearly defined indicators aligned with NHI goals
 - b. Incorporates both quantitative and qualitative measures of health system performance
 - c. Enables real-time adjustments to implementation strategies
2. Independent Oversight: Establish an independent oversight body to obtain the following objectives.
- a. Monitor NHI implementation and expenditure
 - b. Conduct regular audits and evaluations
 - c. Provide transparent reporting to the public and stakeholders
3. Community Feedback Mechanisms: Implement community feedback mechanisms that will accomplish the following goals.
- a. Enable users to provide input on their experiences with NHI services
 - b. Incorporate community perspectives into ongoing policy refinement
 - c. Foster accountability to beneficiaries

4. Research and Learning Agenda: Develop comprehensive research and learning agenda to gain the following objectives.

- a. Evaluate the impact of NHI on health outcomes and health system performance
- b. Identify best practices and lessons learned from implementation
- c. Inform evidence-based policy adjustments

Conclusion

Summary of Findings

This study has thus facilitated comprehensive scrutiny of the NHI policy in South Africa, focusing on policy formulation and stakeholder engagement processes and challenges that attend implementation. The key findings from this study can therefore be summarised as follows:

1. Policy Formulation: NHI's ambitious attempt to attain universal health coverage in South Africa to address inequity in health care has actually been an agonisingly protracted and contentious process of policy formulation, reflecting the complexities of implementing such a sweeping reform in the context of deep socioeconomic disparities.

2. Stakeholder Engagement: While the general opinion seems to be that something needs to be done about the inequities in healthcare, the NHI has been facing strong opposition to its implementation from key stakeholders, such as health professionals and the private sector. The recent boycott of the Presidential Health Compact serves only to illustrate active participation and stakeholder buy-in as an issue.

3. Implementation Challenges: The NHI faces the following implementation challenges.

- a. Financial sustainability concerns in the context of economic constraints
- b. Health system capacity issues, particularly in terms of infrastructure and human resources
- c. Operational complexities in transitioning to a single-payer system
- d. Balancing the roles of public and private sectors
- e. Ensuring quality of care while expanding access

4. Gaps between Policy and Practice: The ambitious goals of NHI policy have significant gaps between them and the actual realities on the ground in funding, health system capacity, and alignment of stakeholders' roles.

5. Political Will and Governance: To date, there has been clear political dedication to the principle of universal health coverage. However, challenges remain regarding translating this commitment to effective action, particularly regarding consistency in policy formulation, governance capacity, and intergovernmental coordination.

6. Potential Unintended Consequences: Implementing the NHI might imply a number of potential unintended

consequences, including disruption in the private healthcare sector, potential impacts on quality of care, and fiscal pressures on other social spending.

Contributions to Policy and Practice

The study makes a critical contribution to policy and practice within the context of health system reform in South Africa and beyond.

1. Comprehensive Policy Analysis: The present study adds to the depth of understanding of the NHI policy formulation process and contributes to a better understanding of the many complexities that arise in designing and implementing universal health coverage policies in middle-income countries.

2. Lessons from Stakeholder Engagement: The analysis of the response of stakeholders, along with the implications of the Health Compact boycott, contributes to these essential insights into the obstacles and significance of an inclusive policy-making process for health system reform.

3. Implementation Framework: The understanding of crucial implementation challenges provides a framework through which policymakers can better prepare for and respond to barriers in implementing comprehensive health system reforms at scale.

4. Comparative Perspectives: Situating the South African NHI within the broader global ambition of universal health coverage, this study provides comparative insights to inform health policy development in other countries.

5. Actionable Recommendations: The recommendations will present how the implementation of NHI can be improved, how stakeholder engagement can be developed, and how collaboration between the public and the private sector can be enhanced.

Final Thoughts on the Future of NHI in South Africa

National Health Insurance provides a seminal opportunity to transform South Africa's health system and correct entrenched inequities that have characterised the post-apartheid era. Many of the issues against NHI implementation are formidable, yet none are insurmountable. The success of the NHI in the future will be pegged on the following aspects.

1. Adaptive Policy Making: Given the complexity of health system reform, an adaptive approach to the implementation of NHI will be decisive. The approach would be typified by continuous learning, flexibility in the modification of policies in light of implementation experiences, and openness to alternative models emerging over time.

2. Inclusive Stakeholder Involvement: To be able to regain trust and create teamwork among stakeholders, the level of inclusiveness in the entire process is going to be high. It would mean genuine involvement, openness in decision-making processes, and a

willingness to find common ground among diverse interests.

3. Strengthening the Health System: Emphasis on health system strengthening, in particular, primary health care and in under-resourced areas, should be drastically undertaken to lay a strong foundation for effective implementation of the NHI.

4. Balancing Ambition and Pragmatism: While the ambitions of NHI are indeed commendable, ways to balance these aspirations with pragmatic implementation strategies that take fiscal and capacity constraints into consideration have to be sought.

5. Learning from Global Experiences: Global experiences on the implementation of universal health coverage reforms can be instructive for South Africa by adopting those strategies that worked well into local implementation.

6. Political Leadership and Governance - Sustained political will, alongside governance and management capacity improvements from every level of the health system, will be required to surmount implementation challenges.

Although the road to the implementation of NHI in South Africa is filled with various obstacles, the NHI still remains a very critical policy initiative to reduce inequities in healthcare and ultimately achieve universal health coverage. Success in this ambitious reform calls for sustained commitment, collaborative effort, and a willingness to adapt and learn at each step of the way in implementation. By responding to the issues raised in this study and implementing recommendations proffered herein, South Africa will be a step closer to realising its dream of quality and equitable healthcare for all its citizens.

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